

In-loop RAS disinfection: Are peracetic acid-based products a promising solution?

CTRLAQUA ANNUAL MEETING, 11 MAY 2022, HAUGESUND

Vasco Mota, PhD
Research Scientist

What is PAA?

Acetic acid

**Hydrogen
peroxide**

Peracetic acid

Water

Strong oxidizing agent: denatures proteins, disrupts cell wall permeability, and oxidizes sulfhydryl and sulfur bonds in proteins, enzymes, and other metabolites

Commercial products solutions contain PAA, hydrogen peroxide and acetic acid

Why is PAA?

Microbicidal activity: bacteria, virus and fungi

Potency at lower concentrations and rapid degradation to neutral compounds

Degrades into harmless residues (acetate, water and carbon dioxide)

Possible local production in large scale

Oxidative species	Chemical formula	Oxidation potential (Volts)
Hydroxyl radical (1)	OH [*]	2.8
Ozone (1)	O ₃	2.1
Peracetic acid (2)	CH ₃ CO ₃ H	1.8
Hydrogen peroxide (1)	H ₂ O ₂	1.8
Hypochlorite ion (1)	OCl ⁻	1.7
Chlorine dioxide (1)	ClO ₂	1.5
Hypochloric acid (3)	HCl	1.5
Chlorine (3)	Cl ₂	1.4
Oxygen (1)	O ₂	1.2

^a International Maritime Organization (2006).

^b Madigan & Martinko, 2006.

^c Wojtenko et al., 2002.

What do we know about PAA use in Aquaculture?

In use as a surface disinfectant or sanitizer in aquaculture facilities.
Not allowed to use as water disinfectant in Norway.

But for example, continuous water PAA dosing is used in rainbow trout farms in Denmark to prevent pathogen outbreaks.

Minor/negligible effects:

- 0.2–1.0 mg/L for rainbow trout (Davidson et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2017)
- 0–2.5 mg/L for salmon smolts and post-smolts (Good et al., 2020; Lazado et al., 2020b; Soleng et al., 2019).

Unknown for Atlantic salmon parr.

It can become another tool in the disinfection toolbox for Norwegian aquaculture.

RASHealth: Water disinfection strategies to improve Atlantic salmon parr production in freshwater recirculating aquaculture systems

Nofima: Vasco Mota (PL), Carlo Lazado, Anne-May Johansen

NTNU: Alexandros Asimakopoulos & Junjie Zhang

DTU Aqua: Lars-Flemming Pedersen & Wanhe Qi

Statistics

Projects

[Back to search](#)

▼ HAVBRUK2-Stort program for havbruksforskning

Water disinfection strategies to improve Atlantic salmon parr production in freshwater recirculating aquaculture systems

Alternative title: Strategier for desinfisering av ferskvann i resirkuleringsystemer i akvakultur, for å forbedre oppdrett av lakseparr.

Awarded: **NOK 8.0 mill.**

Source:	Research council of Norway
Project Manager:	Vasco Mota
Project Number:	302767
Application Type:	Forskerprosjekt / Unge forskertalenter
Project Period:	2020 - 2023
Funding received from:	HAVBRUK2-Stort program for havbruksforskning
Organisation:	Instituttsektor / Primaærnæringsinstitutter / NOFIMA AS
Location:	Troms og Finnmark - Romsa ja Finnmárku - Tromssa ja Finmarkku / Tromsø
Subject Fields:	Landbruks- og fiskerifag / Fiskerifag / Akvakultur
Partner countries:	Danmark

**Acute dose-response exposure of a peracetic acid-based disinfectant to
Atlantic salmon parr reared in RAS**

Material and methods

Nine PAA concentrations (0.0, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.8, 1.6, 3.2 and 6.4 mg/L).

Nine individual RAS units stocked with Atlantic salmon

Experimental design overview

PAA-based product used

2.3. Other hazards

PBT / vPvB

Not PBT / vPvB.

SECTION 3: Composition / information on ingredients

3.2. Mixtures

Substance	Identification	Classification	Contents	Notes
Hydrogen peroxide	CAS No.: 7722-84-1 EC No.: 231-765-0 Index No.: 008-003-00-9 REACH Reg. No.: 01-2119485845-22	Ox. Liq. 1; H271 Acute tox. 4; H302,H332 Skin Corr. 1A; H314 Eye Dam. 1; H318 STOT SE 3; H335 Aquatic Chronic 3; H412	~ 23 %	
Acetic acid	CAS No.: 64-19-7 EC No.: 200-580-7 Index No.: 607-002-00-6 REACH Reg. No.: 01-2119475328-30	Eye Dam. 1; H318 Flam. Liq. 3; H226 Skin Corr. 1A; H314	~ 10 %	
Peracetic acid	CAS No.: 79-21-0 EC No.: 201-186-8 Index No.: 607-094-00-8 REACH Reg. No.: 01-2119531330-56	Flam. Liq. 3; H226 Org. Perox. CD; H242 Acute tox. 4; H302 Acute tox. 4; H332 Acute tox. 4; H312 Skin Corr. 1A; H314 Eye Dam. 1; H318 STOT SE 3; H335 Aquatic Acute 1; H400 Aquatic Chronic 1; H410	~ 5 %	
Substance comments	The full text for all hazard statements is displayed in section 16.			

Sampling

Maia Eggen (MSc student) during sampling

Experimental RAS units and fish at HiT, Tromsø

Results: Survival and swimming behaviour

100 % survival PAA ≤ 1.6 mg/L

Intense erratic activity with occasional gasping for air

Results: Gills

100% necrosis of lamella tissue

healthy gills with well-defined structures

necrotic gills with dead tissue (arrows)

Take home messages

Parr seems not affect at PAA below 1.6 mg/L

PAA is a strong acid and its toxicity in low water alkalinity should be considered.

Not shown:

Longer exposure (4 weeks) of PAA 1 mg/L did not affect parr growth or health.

Mode of application (Pulse vs continuous) seems to not impact fish

PAA-based products are a source of carbon into RAS: proliferation microorganism

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Aquaculture

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/aquaculture

Acute dose-response exposure of a peracetic acid-based disinfectant to Atlantic salmon parr reared in recirculating aquaculture systems

Vasco C. Mota^{a,*}, Maia L. Eggen^b, Carlo C. Lazado^c

^a Nofima AS, The Norwegian Institute of Food, Fisheries and Aquaculture Research, 9291 Tromsø, Norway

^b Faculty of Biosciences, Fisheries and Economics, UiT - the Arctic University of Norway, 9037 Tromsø, Norway

^c Nofima AS, The Norwegian Institute of Food, Fisheries and Aquaculture Research, 1433 Ås, Norway

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Peracetic acid (PAA)
Atlantic salmon parr
Recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS)
Disinfection
Fish health

ABSTRACT

There is a high regard for peracetic acid (PAA)-based disinfectants in recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS) because of the low risk of bioaccumulation, fast degradation with neutral residuals and minimal impact on biofilter performance. However, the no-observed-effect concentration in Atlantic salmon parr is unknown. The present study evaluated the effect of an acute PAA exposure on Atlantic salmon parr health and welfare by evaluating survival, swimming behaviour, appetite and histopathological alterations in the gills and skin. Nine experimental RAS units were employed, where each unit was dedicated for one PAA concentration (0.0, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.8, 1.6, 3.2 and 6.4 mg/L). Fish were exposed to the target PAA concentration in a static system for

Available soon

Accepted

Original Research

Mode of application of peracetic acid-based disinfectants has a minimal influence on the antioxidant defences and mucosal structures of Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) parr

Daniilo Carletto, Francisco Furtado, Junjie Zhang, Alexandros G Asimakopoulos, Maia Eggen, Gerhardus Verstege, Caterina Faggio, Vasco C. Mota and Carlo C. Lazado

Handling Editor:

Alaa El-Din Hamid Sayed

Frontiers in Physiology
Aquatic Physiology

Submitted on
20/03/2022

Accepted on
26/04/2022

Thank you for
your attention!

vasco.mota@nofima.no

Vasco Mota, PhD
Research Scientist

